

Administered Questionnaires

Farmers' Survey

Respondent's data

Gender

Age

Farmer education level

Municipality of the farm headquarter

Farm general information

Total area (size in hectares)

Use of communal lands/civic use lands (yes/no)

Grasslands? (size in hectares)

Cultivated forages? (size in hectares)

Grazing land? (size in hectares)

Number of people working in the livestock farm?

Species of farmed animals?

Number of adult females?

Do you perform manual or mechanical milking?

Technical questions regarding the farm:

Do you practice the RDP animal welfare measures?

If yes, what kind of change did you make in your farm management?

Do you think it is important to adhere to animal welfare practices?

Is it important to have an animal welfare certification for products?

What do you mean by animal welfare?

Can a well treated livestock be more productive?

Do you think that well treated animals get less sick?

Text of invitation posted on Facebook pages

Good evening I am a student in the Faculty of Agriculture at the University of Sassari, I am doing a thesis on livestock ethics and one part is based on animal welfare. Could you help me with the development of the following questionnaire? There are no right or wrong answers and importantly the questionnaire will be anonymous. Thank you to those who decide to fill it out!

Post nel gruppo

Simona Carta ha condiviso un link. ...

30 Ott 2020 · 🌐

Buonasera a tutti.

Sono una studentessa della facoltà di Agraria dell'Università di Sassari, sto svolgendo una tesi sull'etica degli allevamenti e una parte è dedicata al benessere animale. Potreste darmi una mano con lo svolgimento del seguente questionario? Non ci sono risposte giuste o sbagliate e cosa importante il questionario risulterà anonimo.

Grazie a chi deciderà di compilarlo!

👍 Francesco Piras e altre 44 persone

Commenti: 39

Consumers' survey

Respondent's data

Gender

Age

Education

Occupation

City of residence

Does any family member work on a farm?

Awareness of animal welfare

Do you own any pets?

If yes, which pets?

Do you know that animal welfare is strictly regulated in Europe?

In your opinion how the animals are treated in intensive farming?

In your opinion how the animals are treated in extensive farming?

Is animal welfare a priority for you?

Do you think livestock animals have different needs than pets?

Would you be willing to pay more for products with animal welfare certification?

If yes, how much money would you be willing to pay?

Respondent's diet

Are you a meat-eater?

What kind of diet do you follow?

If you are vegetarian or vegan, for what reasons?

Text of invitation posted on Facebook pages

Hello everyone, I am a student at the Faculty of Agriculture in Sassari, I am doing my thesis on animal welfare and I could use the help of as many people as possible in filling out a very short questionnaire. It only takes less than 5 minutes. Thank you to those who would like to respond, I leave below the link to go fill it out. Have a great day everyone

Post nel gruppo

Simona Carta ha condiviso un link. ...
19 Feb 2021 · 🌐

Salve a tutti sono una studentessa della facoltà di Agraria di Sassari, sto svolgendo la tesi sul benessere animale e mi servirebbe l'aiuto di più persone possibili per la compilazione di un brevissimo questionario. Bastano meno di 5 minuti. Grazie a chi vorrà rispondere, lascio di seguito il link per andare a compilarlo. Buona giornata a tutti!

docs.google.com
Benessere animale

👍 Roberta Cresci e altre 210 persone Commenti: 211